

that's what is meant. It means the rain falls here [Ed. Note: on the ocean side of the mountain], and over here [Ed. Note: on the opposite side] there's almost none. So the air rises, resulting in clouds, and ultimately rain or snow falls. That kind of situation is common.

Another kind of situation is where you've got a front. Dr. Schotland talked about fronts. You have a frontal surface. This is cool air here, and warm air rises over the frontal surface. You get clouds developing here, and then you get rain or snow.

So that's, in a sense, another form of mechanical lifting. That's the phrase that some people like to use, in the sense that you have something to obstruct the flow and force the air up.

In the summertime, all over the world, the most frequent cause of vertical air motions is instability of the air in convective clouds. About half of our rain falls in July and August here. And we see the same thing all over the world. In summertime, in the growing season, we get convective clouds, and this comes about because of instability; the atmosphere is unstable. And once you start the air lifting, either because it goes over a hill or because of a frontal surface, the fundamental effect is as follows. I guess Dr. Schotland referred to this. You have a situation where, let's say, this is the cloud, and the temperature decreases with height. This is a plot of height [Ed. Note: along the ordinate] versus temperature [Ed. Note: along the abscissa]. And you send up a balloon [Ed. Note: or cloud] at this point [Ed. Note: point "A"].

Let's say it's summertime and the temperature is about 35°C . You send up a balloon, and as the balloon rises, it measures temperature falling off with height. Let's make the top of the graph 50,000 feet because the temperature starts warming up there [Ed. Note: above 50,000 feet]. This [Ed. Note: point "B"] is the base of the stratosphere. Now, if for some reason or other the air is unstable — and I've pictured it to be unstable here — the air begins to rise. Let's say it goes over a hill. It starts here and rises this way and cools off, and then it keeps cooling off. When it gets up here, this is the "cloud air", and this is what we would call the "environment." So if the cloud starts here [Ed. Note: at point "A"], let's say this is the cloud base. This is the cloud air in here [Ed. Note: area between line AB and the cloud line], and this is the environment [Ed. Note: area below line AB]. So if you have this sort of situation, the cloud air here is warmer than the environment air, when you have an unstable atmosphere. And as long as this air [Ed. Note: the cloud air] is warmer than that, you have a positive buoyancy force. We all

know that warm air is lighter than cool air. So, as long as this [Ed. Note: the cloud air] is warmer than that [Ed. Note: the environment air], this [Ed. Note: the cloud] keeps accelerating upward at increasing speeds. It goes higher and higher. And as long as this continues to stay warmer — as long as the cloud air stays warmer because the temperature increases that way [Ed. Note: from environment to cloud line] — you have a continuing upward force. And it goes upward faster and faster and faster. And it continues rising until it crosses over the point where it's cooler than the environment. At this point right here [Ed. Note: point "B", at 50,000 feet on the graph, preceding page], the cloud air has the same temperature as the surrounding air. And above it, it's the other way around. And above this point, you have a downward force because the cloud air is cooler way up here, and so that cuts off the top, the growth of the cloud.

So this is what's called convection. And the cumulus clouds, the things we see in the summertime around here, big puffy clouds like mushrooms, form that way. They're called convective clouds because it's a convective air motion. That is to say, the air goes up this way and comes down somewhere else.

It's a convection cell, just like you can demonstrate with a can having a little water. Warm it someplace on the bottom, and the water rises. When the water is warm, it rises, and it sinks over there. Because of their depth, it's in these kinds of clouds that you can get all kinds of things happening with rain or snow. You get rain, you get ice particles, they interact, they produce electricity, the charges separate, you get lightning, you get thunder, sometimes you get violent kinds of conditions. At any rate, cumulus clouds are convective clouds.

Now there is one point about clouds which is the crucial point as far as weather modification is concerned. I said last time that people have gone at this about a million ways, but the way that has attracted the most attention recently is to find some kind of instability in the cloud. And the chief instability that people have found in clouds is one having to do with the formation of ice in clouds. Let me elaborate on that.

I've said that the temperature decreases with height. Let's say that this is where the temperature is 0°C , 32°F .

In the Tucson area, in the summertime, that's a height of about 5 kilometers or let's say about 15,000 feet, which isn't very much different from what it is in Illinois in the summertime, or in Florida in the summertime. The height of the freezing level is what it's called — a very poor name, by the way. It shouldn't be called the freezing level, it should be called the "melting level," for reasons that I'll come to. But in the summertime, the air that is over Tucson during the rainy days and the air that's over the Middle West or the Great Plains or Florida, is similar in many respects. It's air that came in from the maritime regions at low latitudes, about 15,000 feet above sea level.

Typically, the cloud bases here in the Tucson area in the summertime are at about 10,000 feet. So the clouds start forming at about 10,000 feet and start growing up. The cloud base does vary from place to place. The typical cloud base here in the summertime is 10,000 feet for cumulus clouds. Over the Great Plains or the Middle Western United States, it may be 5,000 feet. And when you get into the really humid air, in Florida, for example, or Puerto Rico or Panama, the cloud base is down here at 2,000 feet. But that's not too important.

What is important is that the cloud base starts forming at 10,000 feet because the air was rising. It started getting more humid, it reached 100% or pretty close to it, condensation began on these condensation nuclei, a cloud began to form, the air is still rising, and the cloud keeps getting bigger and bigger and bigger. The temperature at the top of the cloud keeps decreasing. The temperature of the cloud top is not too far different than what it is outside the cloud. The temperature difference may be of the order of a degree or two, which for certain purposes is very important, as far as buoyancy. If the cloud air is only one degree warmer than the air around it, the buoyancy forces are very great, so the cloud keeps going up.

But from the point of view of the cloud droplets, let's say the temperatures are very close; they keep getting cooler. And then — this is the 0° isotherm — the cloud develops above the freezing level. Now the temperature here might be as low as -5°C . And the surprising thing is that the water droplets do not freeze. And that to me was a big surprise. I mean why don't they freeze? They would outside your house on a cold winter day. This is 32°F , and 9 degrees down from that is 23°F , and it still hasn't frozen. Well, you know that every time you step outside your door in the morning and the temperature is 23° , if you have a puddle of water there, it's ice; it freezes. But in the atmosphere, it is common, in a rapidly building cumulus cloud, for the cloud droplets not to freeze. They don't even freeze when you get up here as low as -20°C , which is down close to 0°F .

Now how do we know that's true? If you get up there in an airplane, for example, just to give you some notion of the kind of altitude we're talking about, this [Ed. Note: the 0°C level] is at 15,000 feet. You can fly through the cloud at 20,000 feet, a cumulus cloud that's building. Get a decent airplane so you don't worry about it because it's going to be very turbulent. And if you fly through at 20,000 feet, you will find, as you come out the other side of the cloud, that the wings will be covered with ice, not very much ice, but a thin layer of ice, because the cloud is composed of water droplets having a temperature far below freezing.

As soon as they strike the wings of the airplane or the propeller or any solid surface — I'm assuming that you've been flying up here so the airplane is cooled off — as soon as they strike, they freeze. Why don't they freeze without the surface? Because the water is very pure. Cloud droplets are composed of fairly pure water — most of the time, not all of the time. The water down here is all full of crud, you know.

Let's say a cloud droplet formed on a salt particle having a diameter of 1 micron. And then you had a cloud droplet that had a radius of 100 microns, for example. If you have a 1 micron salt particle which grew to a 100 micron water droplet, you would say: What is the quantity of salt as opposed to the quantity of water? You will recall that the volume of a sphere is $\frac{4}{3} \pi r^3$. So if you take the ratio of the volume here [Ed. Note: volume of the salt particle] to the volume here [Ed. Note: volume of the water droplet], it's in ratio to the cube of the radius, which means 1 to 1,000,000. Now, in this case, where I take a fairly big cloud droplet, the concentration of salt will be one part per million, which is not much. At any rate, since the droplets are composed of fairly pure water, as the cloud grows, they do not freeze. They become supercooled, and this is a key word, you'll find. It's just like when you're talking about air pollution, the key word is "temperature inversion"; nobody talks about air pollution without hearing at least once or twice the term "temperature inversion." Nobody talks about weather modification without having used the word "supercooled" half a dozen times. And what it refers to — and this I've said two or three times — is cloud droplets or rain droplets or water droplets in the atmosphere which have temperatures below freezing but which have not frozen.

And on that note we'll have to call it a week.

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